

From the study of the effect of temperature on reaction rate, activation energy and entropy of activation have been found to be 11 kcal mol⁻¹ and -46 e.u. with salicylidene *o*-aminobenzoic acid and 12 kcal mol⁻¹ and -40 e.u. with salicylidene *o*-aminobenzothiol as substrate. The following mechanism explains all the kinetic results :

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Solid State Degradation of Carbamide in Presence of Mixed Metal Oxides

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TRANSITION metal oxides with perovskite structure have been the subject of intensive investigations because of their interesting electrical and magnetic properties¹. The nature of defects as well as other

surface properties in many systems are yet to be studied. For example, not much is known about the catalytic properties of perovskite oxides. Presently we report the catalytic properties of LaMO₃ (M=Co, Ni) activated at different temperatures for the solid state degradation of carbamide.

Experimental

LaCoO₃ prepared by the oxalate methods², so was subjected to heat-treatment at 973, 1073, 1173 and 1273 K for 18 h. LaNiO₃ prepared³ was activated similarly. Commercial sample of carbamide was used. Excess surface oxygen (E.S.O.) and acidity of the samples were measured by the reported methods⁴.

The process and apparatus used for the kinetic study of degradation of urea were the same as adopted by Prasad and Bhagat⁴. The decomposition of a mixture of carbamide and catalyst (20 : 1) was performed at three different temperatures, viz. 413, 423 and 433 K. A plot between log (V_∞ - V_t) and time (t) was drawn, V_∞ being the volume of ammonia measured at infinite time and V_t the volume of ammonia at the time (t).

Results and Discussion

The rate constants were calculated from the initial slopes of the rate curves, -log (V_∞ - V_t) vs t (time). Energy of activation and frequency factor were calculated from the Arrhenius plots (log K vs t). Obviously the degradation of carbamide in presence of our samples obeys the first order kinetics. The values of rate constant, energy of activation and frequency factor are recorded in Table 1.

It is clear from the data (Table 1) that all the samples activated at different temperature catalyse the degradation of carbamide though their degree of catalytic activities for the thermal decomposition of urea seem to be different. Taking the values of specific rate constants in consideration, it is to be concluded that there is no regular pattern between the catalytic activities of the samples and the temperature of activation. This is also reflected from the values of energy of activation. However, the samples of LaCoO₃ activated at 1073 and 1173 K

TABLE I—KINETIC DATA FOR DEGRADATION OF CARBAMIDE

Sample	Activation temp. K	Specific rate (× 10 ⁻⁴ s ⁻¹) at			E _a kcal mol ⁻¹	log A	E.S.O./g of sample × 10 ⁻³	Acidity meq./g
		419 K	423 K	433 K				
Carbamide alone		2.78	5.23	6.75	12.25	8.00	—	—
LaCoO ₃	973	9.58	14.22	16.88	10.06	5.39	11.20	128.48
	1 073	12.27	15.35	17.90	6.65	3.54	7.12	112.42
	1 173	11.52	17.27	18.42	8.13	4.29	6.48	102.93
	1 273	8.37	12.78	17.05	12.20	6.45	5.84	98.07
LaNiO ₃	973	10.23	15.35	18.42	10.56	5.85	10.40	157.31
	1 073	13.82	16.88	18.60	4.88	2.56	7.60	144.54
	1 173	13.82	18.42	21.10	7.93	4.16	5.60	129.95
	1 273	9.58	14.32	18.42	11.52	6.26	5.44	115.24

found to be a bit more active than the samples activated at 973 and 1273 K. Similar observation with respect to the catalytic activity is also recorded (Table 1) in case of LaNiO_3 .

As reported in the literature⁶ the degraded products of carbamide decomposition at low temperature which occurs in two steps are biuret and ammonia. Our experimental data also support the scheme.

Fig. 1 shows the plots of volume of ammonia obtained against the time for the thermal degradation of carbamide without and with the sample of LaCoO_3 activated at 973 K. Similar plots have also been obtained in case of the samples of LaNiO_3 .

Fig. 1. Kinetics of degradation of carbamide: (1), (2), (3) urea, and (4), (5), (6) (urea + sample) at 413, 423 and 433 K respectively.

It is to be noted that all the samples activate the degradation of carbamide although their degree of activation differs. From plots (volume of ammonia vs time) the simple calculation yields 93.33, 156.66 and 223.33 mm^3 of NH_3 at 413, 423 and 433 K respectively in 10 s. However with the samples of LaNiO_3 activated at 973 K, 110.00, 176.66 and 253.33 mm^3 of NH_3 are obtained at the corresponding temperature in the same specified time from the same quantity of urea. These observations conclude that samples of perovskite type oxide containing Ni appear catalytically more active in comparison to that containing Co. This is also obvious from the rate constant data presented in Table 1.

Table 1 also contains the data on excess surface oxygen (E.S.O.) and acidity of our sample. These values decrease regularly with the rise in temperature of activation of the samples. Similar variation in the values of E.S.O. of LaCoO_3 with the rise in calcination temperature has been reported by Madhok⁶. However, from the analysis of our experimental data we conclude that the E.S.O. and

acidity seem to play no significant role towards the catalytic activity of the samples.

The plots of $\log A$ vs E_a (energy of activation) values show linear relationship. It indicates that the active centres are chiefly transition metal ion, i.e. Ni^{2+} in LaNiO_3 and Co^{2+} , Co^{3+} in LaCoO_3 . Thus, the variation in activity of the samples might be attributed to the different amount of transition metal ionic species distributed on the surface. Similar type of observation has been reported by Johnson (Jr.) *et al.*⁷ for the catalytic activity of LaMeO_3 oxide (Me = Fe, Co, Mn) for the oxidation of Co.

Thus, it is concluded that the transition metal ions are responsible for the activity of the LaMO_3 type oxides and rare earth ions moderate the catalytic activity of the transition metal ions.

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Studies on the Effect of Alkali on the Compounds related to Aminoimidazoliumcarboxamides

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1,3-Disubstituted-4-amino-5-carboxamidoimidazolium salts undergo base-catalysed Dimroth type rearrangement to produce 1-alkyl-4-substituted-aminoimidazole-5-carboxamides^{1,2}. Presence of bulky groups on imidazolium nitrogens, however, leads to a pyrazine ring formation in similar treatment reported recently³. These observations provided impetus to study the effect of the groups on N_1 and N_3 of aminoimidazolecarboxamide and its